

A Causal Relationship Between Phenylketonuria and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder Relating
to Obsessive-Compulsive-Like Behaviors and Structural Changes in the Brain

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Abstract

Phenylketonuria (PKU) is a genetic metabolic disorder that stems from the body's inability to process the amino acid phenylalanine (Phe). This leads to the buildup of Phe in the brain, which can result in severe intellectual disabilities when left untreated. Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is a mental health disorder in which an individual experiences obsessions and/or compulsions. While there have been studies that investigate behaviors in people with PKU, there are a limited number of studies that explore PKU in direct relationship to OCD. This study conducted a meta-analysis with the aim of developing the understanding of PKU and OCD by researching if the two have a causal relationship. Specifically, the topic of inquiry was if and to what extent PKU contributes to the development of OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on the occurrence of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors and structural changes in the brain. The analysis was conducted via a fixed effects model. Two statistical analyses were conducted, one on behavior and one on brain. Four studies were used in each analysis. The effect sizes and later the variance of each of the eight studies used were calculated. These values were then assigned individual weights and were used to compute the pooled effect size to determine the strength of the relationship between PKU and OCD. It was determined that PKU substantially contributes to the likelihood of developing subsyndromal OCD due to its effect on OCD-related behaviors, but does not considerably contribute to the likelihood of developing diagnosed OCD due to its minimal effect on inducing OCD-related neurological changes.

Keywords: phenylketonuria, obsessive-compulsive disorder, behavior, brain, meta-analysis

Introduction

Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) is the fourth most common mental health disorder with an estimated prevalence of 2.3% in the United States alone (Pampaloni et al., 2022). According to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)*, OCD consists of obsessions and/or compulsions which cause significant distress or impairment in functioning (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Obsessions are recurrent and persistent thoughts, urges, or images while compulsions are repetitive behaviors or mental acts that the individual feels compelled to perform in response to an obsession (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Individuals may also experience subsyndromal OCD which are cases in which they meet some but not all of the necessary criteria for diagnosis (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Phenylketonuria (PKU), on the other hand, is a metabolic disorder caused by a genetic mutation of the phenylalanine hydroxylase (PAH) gene (Dijkstra et al., 2021). The mutation inhibits the body's ability to break down and convert the amino acid phenylalanine (Phe) into the amino acid tyrosine (Tyr), causing its accumulation into the blood and brain (Dijkstra et al., 2021). This often leads to the individual experiencing seizures, microcephaly (small head size), eczema, etc. (Thomas et al., 2024).

With the emergence of research on OCD and its effect on a person's quality of life, there have been advancements to treatment for OCD. Treatments for PKU, however, have been limited primarily to lifelong dietary plans with restrictions on high-protein food since its discovery in 1934 (Woolf and Adams, 2020). Currently, there are limited studies investigating the relationship between the two. This study aimed to investigate if and to what extent PKU contributes to the likelihood of developing OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on data collected on the occurrence of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors and structural changes in the

brain. Using a meta-analysis approach, these data were collected from peer-reviewed, scholarly studies. In doing so, this study attempted to use its findings to improve current treatments for both OCD and PKU.

Literature Review

OCD and the Brain

Current research on OCD typically focuses on how it may impact one's social or occupational functioning and its impact on structures of the brain. These studies, however, are typically limited to OCD by itself as opposed to investigating how OCD may be caused or exacerbated by external factors. Fouche et al. (2022), for example, conducted a meta-analysis to research subcortical (deep brain structures) shape in people with OCD, omitting the mention of external causes. Similar to the findings from researchers Wang et al. (2022), they found that when comparing OCD patients with comorbid depression or anxiety to healthy controls, certain structures had lower surface area while others had greater surface area (Fouche et al., 2022). The present study similarly gathered data on affected subcortical structures as they are vital in carrying out functions such as motor control, emotion, memory, etc. (Wang et al., 2022). Wang et al. (2022) likewise contend that patients with OCD had altered amygdala shape which correlated with symptom severity (Wang et al., 2022). Luo et al. (2021) also examined OCD's influence on the brain. Rather than focusing on subcortical shape, however, they found that individuals with OCD demonstrated decreased temporal variability of connectivity and efficiency in two structures of the brain: the precuneus and middle front gyrus (Luo et al., 2021). Although these differ from the primary structures that will be looked at in this study, the precuneus and middle front gyrus also play crucial roles in the same executive functions as subcortical structures such as cognitive processing (Luo et al., 2021).

PKU and the Brain

While the studies above researched OCD, it is necessary to discuss the current body of literature for OCD. The buildup of Phe often has significant effects in the brain, ranging from impacts on cognitive function to neuropsychological function (Dijkstra et al., 2021). Current research acknowledges that these neurological changes may occur, with some studies even detailing the neural mechanisms behind them, but fewer studies go further and connect these changes to other disorders. Muri et al. (2024), for instance, researched the consequences of high Phe levels in patients with PKU, finding that patients with untreated PKU often develop abnormal neural connections that can lead to cognitive impairment and intellectual disability. In another study, Muri et al. (2022) investigated high Phe exposure specifically on cortical thickness, discovering that in a majority of cases it was significantly reduced. Apart from changes in subcortical structures, studies have also researched alterations in chemical concentrations in the brain. Dijkstra et al. (2021) examined these alterations, determining that Phe concentrations were significantly correlated to serotonin and dopamine levels (Dijkstra et al., 2021). Although Dijkstra et al. (2021) and Muri et al. (2024) researched different neurological components, both studies relate back to the understanding that PKU may be associated with lowered cognitive function. This study included data on all three elements (neural mechanisms, cortical structures, and chemical concentrations) to address the gap of how all three components are related to PKU.

PKU and Behavior

Aside from affecting the brain, PKU also influences behavior. These behaviors include impulsive-hyperactivity, anxiety, conduct issues, etc. (Xue et al., 2025). When regarding obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors, this paper defined them in accordance with the *DSM-5*'s

definition of OCD. Xue et al. (2025) evaluated the prevalence of psycho-behavioral difficulties in children with PKU, concluding that PKU may contribute to the behaviors mentioned above. Their study, however, is limited to children. Despite including that the behaviors are oftentimes followed into adulthood, they do not include individuals over the age of 18 in their research. In contrast, Ashe et al. (2019) studied the existing literature on psychiatric aspects of PKU, including in adults. Although they briefly mentioned OCD, noting that it has been associated with low serotonin in the brain, they do not go beyond this assertion by attributing if its development is related to PKU. Furthermore, Thiele et al. (2021) explored psychological strengths and weaknesses in individuals with PKU. In terms of strength, they concluded that patients with PKU were within a healthy range for peer interactions (Thiele et al., 2021). For weaknesses, nevertheless, they found that in over 50% of cases, children showed conduct problems and were prone to problems with emotional regulation (Thiele et al., 2021). Although they focused on both strengths and weaknesses as opposed to Xue et al. (2025) who focused primarily on weaknesses, both sources agreed that PKU may contribute to conduct issues.

Gap

When discussing the body of literature for the three components of this topic, there is a gap between the understanding of how they all relate to each other. Therefore, this study aimed to research: how and to what extent does PKU influences one's likelihood of developing OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on the occurrence of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors and structural changes in the brain? Currently, there is a developed understanding of PKU's physiological effects and how these effects can be combatted via pharmaceutical treatments. However, there are fewer studies on PKU's effect on mental health and how it may influence

one's likelihood of developing other disorders, let alone OCD specifically. By merging the subtopics of OCD and the brain, PKU and the brain, and PKU and behavior, this study seeks to investigate a connection. The initial hypothesis was that PKU strongly increases one's likelihood of developing subsyndromal OCD due to both behavioral and neurological similarities. This was developed based on preliminary research on PKU and OCD, with the finding that both can contribute to cognitive impairment and may lead to conduct issues. It was assumed that in studies where individuals report OCD-related behaviors, the behaviors were due to PKU and not an external influence.

Methodology

In order to examine the potential relationship between PKU and OCD, this study conducted a meta-analysis using studies that focused on compulsive behaviors and structural changes in the brains of individuals with PKU and/or OCD. Meta-analyses are studies that analyze the findings from previously conducted studies to come to a new understanding of a topic (Leedy & Ormrod, 2019, pp. 220). They focus on gathering secondary, quantitative data that are then interpreted using statistical models (Leedy & Ormrod, 2019, pp. 220). This method was the most feasible and ethical way to study the relationship between PKU and OCD since it allows for an in depth understanding of topics that are otherwise unethical to directly research. Conducting a meta-analysis also ensured the safety and well-being of participants. Participants were not directly involved in this study, but were involved through secondary research. Data were extracted from studies that explicitly followed ethical guidelines such as voluntary participation, disclosure of results, informed consent, anonymity, potential for harm, etc. Ownby et al. (2006) from the Journal of American Medical Association JAMA also conducted a meta-analysis in which they investigated the relationship between depression and Alzheimer's

Disease. Through inclusion and exclusion criteria along with keywords, they extracted data from 20 selected studies and used metaregression analyses for their data analysis. This study was conducted in a similar way in regard to the method used to explore the research question and the process used to select sources. PKU is a very rare disease that affects approximately one in 15,000 people (Brown & Lichter-Konecki, 2016). If the study were to gather data directly from participants via an experimental approach, the limited results would be insufficient to apply to a broader population and could result in an overestimation of the conclusions. Additionally, a mixed-methods study in which qualitative data would have been gathered was not well-suited for the range of this study and would have been unethical to attempt to form conclusions with. Studying participants' brains would also require a high level of expertise and access to specialized equipment such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) machines, CT scanners, and advanced monitors, which were unrealistic for the scope of this study.

Data Collection

One type of data that was collected was on the obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors experienced by individuals with PKU. To maintain consistency in findings, obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors were defined according to the *DSM-5* (Appendix E). The second type of data collected was numerical measurements of structural changes in the brains of individuals with PKU or OCD. These structures included the amygdala, hippocampus, gray matter, and white matter, as they all play crucial roles in regulating cognition and emotion. These changes were compared across the brains of individuals with PKU versus OCD. Data from sources were recorded in a table containing various columns and subsections (Appendices A and B).

Before the collection of data could begin, extensive inclusion and exclusion criteria were implemented in order to gather sources that were relevant, accurate, and well-suited to the goal of the study. The inclusion criteria were established as following:

- All studies must present quantitative data.
- Studies must relate to PKU and/or OCD
- Studies relating to PKU must involve adult humans diagnosed with PKU.
- Studies relating to OCD must involve participants who were either diagnosed with OCD or experience OCD-related symptoms.
- Studies must measure either the chosen brain structures (amygdala, hippocampus, gray matter, and/or white matter) or the chosen behaviors (repetitive behaviors, guilt, anxiety, and/or depression).
- Studies must use validated tools of measurement.
- Experimental studies must have been conducted in accordance with all necessary ethical guidelines as per their respective Institutional Review Boards (IRBs).
- Studies must be peer-reviewed.
- Studies must be published between the years 2015-2025.

Exclusion criteria were then outlined as guidelines for studies that were not fit to be included in the study. They were established as following:

- Studies not involving either PKU or OCD.
- Studies that involve either PKU or OCD, but do not include the chosen brain structures (amygdala, hippocampus, gray matter, and/or white matter) or the chosen behaviors (repetitive behaviors, guilt, anxiety, and/or depression)
- Studies that do not report numerical data.

- Studies that have not been peer-reviewed.
- Studies published before the year 2015.

To gather sources for the analysis, the databases Google Scholar, PubMed, and EBSCOHost were used. These databases have been well-established by researchers, specifically those in scientific disciplines, and are reputable in managing a large collection of sources relating to various fields of study. Keywords relating to PKU and OCD were used to narrow down the search and identify appropriate sources. The following keywords were chosen because they include the neurobiological and behavioral aspects needed to ensure this study fully captured all elements of the topic of inquiry: “phenylketonuria,” “PKU,” “obsessive-compulsive disorder,” “OCD,” “phenylalanine,” “brain,” “amygdala,” “hippocampus,” “gray matter,” “white matter,” “repetitive,” “guilt,” “anxiety,” and “depression.”

Data Analysis

To interpret the data gathered, meta-analyses use statistical models specific for analyzing numerical data. A majority of the models used by researchers require a high level of expertise in statistics and advanced tools that were beyond the feasibility of this study. For this reason, a fixed effects model was used as it is able to be conducted using a combination of a graphing calculator, spreadsheets, a paper, and pencil. This model is primarily used by researchers in psychology and medical fields as it accounts for variability across findings by assigning different weights to data based on its significance and consistency.

Data were first recorded via a table created in Google Sheets designed to classify parts of the study and what was being measured. Google Sheets allowed for simplicity and efficiency when organizing data, better preventing errors when transferring data. The data that were used in calculations were the mean values and the standard deviation (SD) values. The mean value is the

average of all of the values and the SD value is a measure of how close each value is to the mean (average). These values were directly extracted from studies as they are included in the studies' data tables. They were then used to calculate the pooled standard deviation (SD) values and the variables Cohen's *d* and Hedges' *g* using mathematical formulas (Appendix C). These variables are used in the analysis to standardize and interpret the data. The pooled SD values were used to standardize each unit of data and the variables were used to calculate the input values used in the data analysis. The variance of each Hedges' *g* was calculated and assigned its specific weight using another mathematical formula (Appendix C). This weight allowed for specific units of data to hold a larger effect on the overall result. The pooled Hedges' *g*, also known as the overall effect size, was calculated using each Hedges' *g* and its respective weight and ultimately used to determine the magnitude of the causal relationship between PKU and OCD (Appendix C).

Though a meta-analysis was the most efficient method for this study, some limitations were encountered. The two major limitations were meta-analyses' susceptibility to heterogeneity across studies and the risk of selecting studies in which the researcher's findings are inaccurate. Heterogeneity across studies refers to the fact that the studies chosen have all used different procedures, tools of measurement, samples, etc. This poses the risk of inconsistency among the findings which could hinder its application to a larger population. Additionally, when selecting studies, the risk of selecting studies that may have inaccuracies or ethical concerns is present. To avoid these risks as best as possible, strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were followed when identifying the studies that were to be used.

Results

This study used a meta-analysis approach to analyze how and to what extent PKU influences one's likelihood of developing OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on the

frequency of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors they experience and structural changes in their brain. Secondary quantitative data were gathered by screening through empirical studies that published their findings on PKU and/or OCD. Studies were found via the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) model, which is a flow diagram that displays the number of sources included and excluded. Keywords that narrowed down the search were used to identify studies, which were then included or excluded via the inclusion criteria.

Figure 1: *PRISMA Flow Diagram of Studies Included and Excluded*

Note: Flow diagram created in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021).

Figure 1 displays that 83 studies were screened, 41 of which were excluded as they did not meet the criteria necessary for data extraction. Of these 41, 23 were assessed for eligibility; seven studies were eligible and provided data that were used for the analysis. All studies used were published between the years 2015-2025 to ensure recency and relevancy to the current understanding of PKU and OCD. The studies were not limited to the United States, allowing for a broader scope, especially given that PKU is a rare disorder which may not encompass a large number of studies if just limited to the United States.

Quantitative Results on the Frequency of Obsessive-Compulsive-Like Behaviors

The first component of data collection for this study was the frequency of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors in individuals with PKU. The studies used for the analysis measured these behaviors through the following validated self-report questionnaires: the Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) scale, the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), and the Phenylketonuria Quality of Life. Studies that used these three scales were included as they indirectly measure behaviors that are also considered akin to obsessive-compulsive as per the guidelines of the *DSM-5* (Appendix E). These behaviors include: repetitive behaviors, guilt, anxiety, and depression. In Figure 2, the findings of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors in people with PKU are displayed.

Figure 2: *Obsessive-Compulsive-Like Behaviors in People With PKU*

Note: The y-values are the Hedges' g values which typically range from -2 to 2. Values closer to 0 indicate little to no effect, while values greater than 0.8 indicate a large effect.

Figure 2 shows the extent to which individuals with PKU experienced obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors. A higher y -value indicates a stronger frequency that the individual experienced the behavior. Anxiety showed the strongest correlation ($g = 0.98$) while repetitive behaviors showed the weakest correlation ($g = 0.69$). All four behaviors analyzed ranged from

0.69 to 0.98, indicating that participants with PKU strongly experienced behaviors akin to those classified as OCD behaviors.

Quantitative Results on Structural Changes Within the Brain

The second component of this study's data collection included analyzing changes in the structures of the brains of individuals with PKU or OCD. The specific structures that were included were: amygdala, hippocampus, gray matter, and white matter. These structures were included as they all play crucial roles in regulating cognition and emotion. Additionally, the functions of these structures all involve producing motor output, rather than receiving sensory input, which is a distinctive quality of both PKU and OCD (Ashe et al., 2019; Bischof et al., 2024). The method for measuring these structures across studies was typically via MRI. These machines allow researchers to obtain highly detailed images of participants' brains.

Figure 3: *Reductions in Brain Structures Caused by PKU or OCD*

Note: The y-values are the Hedges' g values which typically range from -2 to 2. Values closer to 0 indicate little to no effect, while values greater than 0.8 indicate a large effect.

Figure 3 displays the data that were gathered from four studies. Both OCD and PKU showed reductions in the brain structures hippocampus, amygdala, gray matter, and white matter. There were significantly larger reductions in the hippocampus and amygdala caused by PKU, but weaker reductions in gray matter and white matter. Conversely, there were significantly larger reductions in gray matter and white matter caused by OCD, but weaker reductions in the hippocampus and amygdala.

Analysis

The results above prompt interpretation of the data and how this relates to the study's goal of determining if and to what extent a causal relationship exists between PKU and OCD. Figures 2 and 3 display the data that were gathered from seven sources. From each source, the means and SD were recorded from the experimental and control groups. Through mathematical calculations, these values were used to first calculate the pooled SD values, a weighted average of all of the SD values. The pooled SD for each group of data was then used to calculate Cohen's d , which is a variable that standardizes the data into one consistent format. Each Cohen's d value was used to calculate Hedges' g , the variable that was used to interpret the data. After collecting each Hedges' g value, the variance of each was found and converted into its respective weight. Lastly, the sum of each g along with its corresponding weight was used to calculate the pooled Hedges' g (overall effect size). This pooled Hedges' g gave a single numerical output that determines the magnitude of the causation between PKU and OCD. Table 1 below displays each variable before calculating the overall effect size. The raw data tables that include the values used to calculate the values in Table 1 and Table 2 can be found in Appendix D.

Table 1: Pooled SD, Cohen's d and Hedges' g values for each group of data

Outcome measured	Pooled SD	Cohen's d	Hedges' g
Repetitive Behaviors	23.48	0.70	0.69
Guilt	7.84	0.94	0.93
Anxiety	6.35	0.95	0.98
Depression (PKU)	7.65	0.90	0.89
Hippocampus (PKU)	0.028	-0.72	-0.71
Amygdala (PKU)	0.010	-0.78	-0.77
Gray Matter (PKU)	11876.94	-0.12	-0.12
White Matter (PKU)	6426.48	0.30	0.31
Hippocampus (OCD)	342.88	-0.14	-0.13
Amygdala (OCD)	193.44	-0.11	-0.11
Gray Matter (OCD)	13302.77	0.57	0.55
White Matter (OCD)	7208.08	0.92	0.91

Note: The absolute values of the values in the highlighted column represent the y-values seen on the graphs of Figures 2 and 3.

Table 2 displays each variable used to calculate the overall effect size, as well as the overall effect size (pooled Hedges' g) values. The pooled Hedges' g value was calculated separately for behavioral measurements and neurological measurements in order to accurately analyze the relationship between PKU and OCD within each specific category.

Table 2: *Variance, Weight, and Pooled Hedges' g value(s)*

Outcome measured	Variance	Weight
Repetitive Behaviors	0.047	21.26
Guilt	0.100	9.99
Anxiety	0.100	9.99
Depression (PKU)	0.045	22.19
Hippocampus (PKU)	0.102	9.83
Amygdala (PKU)	0.102	9.81
Gray Matter (PKU)	0.101	9.91
White Matter (PKU)	0.102	9.83
Hippocampus (OCD)	0.0057	175.44
Amygdala (OCD)	0.0057	175.44
Gray Matter (OCD)	0.0561	17.83
White Matter (OCD)	0.0933	10.72
Pooled Hedges' g Value (Behavioral)	—	0.88
Pooled Hedges' g Value (Neurological)	—	-0.02

Note: The pooled Hedges' g value determines the overall effect PKU has on OCD. Hedges' g values which typically range from -2 to 2. Values closer to 0 indicate little to no effect, while values greater than 0.8 indicate a large effect.

Analyzing the Obsessive-Compulsive-Like Behaviors Within PKU

Figure 2 displays the extent to which people with PKU exhibited obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors. All four behaviors yielded a Hedges' g value of 0.69 or above, with guilt, anxiety, and depression yielding values between 0.89 and 0.98. These are considered to be very large numbers and represent a large effect, signifying that people with PKU were more inclined to

experience behaviors similar to those with OCD, compared to people without PKU. With repetitive behaviors resulting in the lowest value ($g = 0.69$), this suggests that of the four OCD-related behaviors analyzed, repetitive behaviors showed the weakest connection to PKU but still maintained a strong tendency to occur. The largest value was yielded by anxiety ($g = 0.98$), supporting that anxiety was the most likely behavior to be observed. In relation to the research question, the consistent behavioral patterns support the conclusion that individuals with PKU strongly exhibit OCD-related behaviors.

Analyzing Structural Changes Within the Brain

In Figure 3, the hippocampus, amygdala, gray matter, and white matter were all analyzed based on its size reduction within brain regions in OCD and PKU. For OCD, gray matter and white matter yielded the most drastic reductions ($g = 0.55$, $g = 0.91$), while the hippocampus and amygdala were not as significantly affected ($g = 0.13$, $g = 0.11$). PKU, however, showed a nearly opposite trend. The Hedges' g values were the highest for the hippocampus and amygdala ($g = 0.71$, $g = 0.77$) but were the lowest for gray matter and white matter ($g = 0.12$, $g = 0.31$). Consequently, OCD and PKU do not exhibit strong correlations in regard to its effect on the neurological structures analyzed. This suggests that PKU and OCD likely do not have a considerable causal relationship in terms of similarities in reductions within the brain.

Overall Effect Sizes

After assigning each variable its respective weight, the pooled Hedges' g was calculated for both themes: behavioral and neurological. The behavioral pooled Hedges' g value was 0.88, a value considered to be very high. This indicates a strong causal relationship between PKU and OCD. However, the neurological Hedges' g value was -0.02, a value very close to 0. This contradictorily indicates a weak causal relationship between PKU and OCD.

Interpretation of Results

This study aimed to analyze how and to what extent PKU influences one's likelihood of developing OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on the frequency of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors they experience and structural changes in their brain. Using a meta-analysis approach, this study was able to form an understanding that responded to the study's research question. This was concluded based on the finding that PKU tended to strongly induce behaviors similar to those categorized as OCD behaviors, but did not bring about changes in the brain that are similar to changes caused by OCD. Although data on obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors indicated a strong likelihood of developing OCD, the data on brain structures did not agree with this conclusion. This aligns with subsyndromal OCD in that individuals are more inclined to experience OCD-related behaviors but do not meet the full criteria for diagnosis of OCD. Thus, it was concluded that PKU substantially contributes to the likelihood of developing subsyndromal OCD due to its effect on OCD-related behaviors, but does not considerably contribute to the likelihood of developing diagnosed OCD due to its minimal effect on inducing OCD-related neurological changes.

Conclusion

In researching if and to what extent PKU influences one's likelihood of developing OCD or subsyndromal OCD in adults, based on behaviors and neurological changes, this study conducted a meta-analysis in which secondary quantitative data were collected. It was established that PKU strongly contributed to the development of subsyndromal OCD rather than diagnosed OCD. Essentially, PKU was found to be strongly associated with individuals experiencing OCD-related behaviors. However, it was weakly associated with structural changes in the brain similar to those caused by OCD. This pattern aligned with subsyndromal OCD as

subsyndromal OCD characterizes cases in which an individual may experience obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors but may not necessarily experience the full effect of OCD that would otherwise induce OCD-related changes in brain structures. This relates back to existing studies that discuss how PKU may influence one's behavior. Before this study was conducted, it had been established by researchers (e.g., Ashe et al., 2019; Xue et al., 2025) that PKU can contribute to the development of behaviors, including, but not limited to, conduct issues, learning difficulties, and impulsive-hyperactivity. However, PKU had not yet been examined with the specific focus of obsessive-compulsive-like behaviors. Additionally, there were even fewer studies relating to how PKU can impact the brain, specifically in connection to OCD. Dijkstra et al. (2021), for example, reported that PKU may lead to increased serotonin and dopamine levels in the brain. However, they do not discuss specific structures within the brain nor do they mention OCD or other mental health disorders.

This understanding both supports and refutes the initial hypothesis that PKU would strongly increase one's likelihood of developing subsyndromal OCD due to both behavioral and neurological similarities. While it was found that PKU does in fact contribute to the development of subsyndromal OCD, to a large extent, this was due to strictly behavioral similarities as opposed to neurological similarities. Before data collection began, it was assumed that in studies where individuals report OCD-related behaviors, the behaviors were due to PKU and not an external influence. This was primarily a consistent pattern throughout where studies accounted for outside influences to ensure accurate attributions of certain behaviors to PKU. However, there were nonetheless a few studies where researchers acknowledged outside factors that could have affected the results. Parolisi et al. (2023), for example, discussed the limitation that "the influence of education may represent a confounding factor (bias)" (Parolisi et al., 2023),

indicating that education may have been an external factor that could have influenced the behaviors that participants exhibited. Although they presented that this could have hindered the applicability of their results, the study ultimately still ensured that their method included validated scales and proper control groups to ensure accuracy in their findings.

Limitations

This study was met with limitations that potentially inhibited the study's effectiveness. One major limitation was meta-analyses' risk of heterogeneity across studies. This refers to the inconsistency between different studies and their method of gathering data. An example of an inconsistency throughout was the age of adult participants. This study focused on adults but there were nonetheless variations across studies, with some including adults over the age of 50 while others including adults under the age of 40. As a result, some of the findings could have been limited in their applicability to a large population. To combat this limitation as best as possible, strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to restrict studies to those that used widely validated tools of measurement. Another significant limitation was the risk of selecting studies that did not ensure accurately reported results. This can include slight miscalculations in the reported mean and SD values or not acknowledging other conditions that participants may have that could interfere with their scores. This would have overall hindered the accuracy of this study's results and potentially modified the reached conclusion. This limitation was mitigated by filtering through each study's method and noting down whether they were replicable and defended. It was also considered if the studies were peer-reviewed and conducted by specialized researchers.

Implications

The implications of this study are spread across a variety of fields and disciplines. The most prominent implication is the findings' ability to contribute to current treatment for PKU. Current treatments for PKU are typically limited to medication, with therapeutic treatments less frequently employed. The study's main findings that PKU substantially increases one's likelihood of developing subsyndromal OCD through behavioral similarities could support future proposals of implementing a combined treatment plan which incorporates therapeutic treatment. The findings of this study are also relevant to researchers who specifically research metabolic diseases, genetic disorders, and mental health disorders. This understanding could encourage an interdisciplinary approach in which researchers study physical health in conjunction with mental health. Furthermore, these findings could even be applied outside of the health science discipline, to education studies. The correlation between PKU and OCD-related behaviors can increase awareness among educational professionals and introduce new approaches to instructing students. It may also encourage them to educate students on what PKU is and how physiological health can influence mental health, reducing misunderstandings and stigma within school environments.

Future Directions

In order to develop a more sophisticated understanding of how PKU and mental health are interrelated, further research should be conducted analyzing disorders beyond OCD. Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), anxiety disorders, and behavioral disorders, are among the many types that could potentially be influenced by PKU. In addition to research on PKU and mental health, future research could expand to include a converse relationship: how psychological health may influence physiological conditions. While it has been established by many researchers (e.g., Lou et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2023) that mental health-induced stress can

have significant effects on one's cortisol levels and the strength of their heart and immune system, there have been fewer studies that focus on additional factors such as emotional suppression, health anxiety, and social rejection sensitivity. In doing so, researchers will be able to garner a better understanding of individuals' health as a whole, including both mental and physical health, and can further advance how both are perceived.

References

- Albers, A., Kuniß, N., Kloos, C., Wolf, G., Schmidt, S., & Müller, N. (2026). Navigating adulthood with PKU: Metabolic outcomes, quality of life, and mental health 4.5 years post-transition. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-025-04186-1>
- Aldridge, K., Cole, K. K., Moffitt Gunn, A. J., Peck, D., White, D. A., & Christ, S. E. (2020). The effects of early-treated phenylketonuria on volumetric measures of the cerebellum. *Molecular Genetics and Metabolism Reports*, *25*, 100647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymgmr.2020.100647>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (5th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596>
- Ashe, K., Kelso, W., Farrand, S., Panetta, J., Fazio, T., De Jong, G., & Walterfang, M. (2019). Psychiatric and cognitive aspects of phenylketonuria: The limitations of diet and promise of new treatments. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, *10*(561). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00561>
- Bischof, C., Hohensee, N., Fanny Alexandra Dietel, Doebler, P., Klein, N., & Buhlmann, U. (2024). Emotion regulation in obsessive-compulsive disorder: An ecological momentary assessment study. *Behavior Therapy*, *55*(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beth.2024.01.011>
- Brown, C. S., & Lichter-Konecki, U. (2016). Phenylketonuria (PKU): A problem solved? *Molecular Genetics and Metabolism Reports*, *6*(6), 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymgmr.2015.12.004>

- Dijkstra, A. M., van Vliet, N., van Vliet, D., Romani, C., Huijbregts, S. C. J., van der Goot, E., Hovens, I. B., van der Zee, E. A., Kema, I. P., Heiner-Fokkema, M. R., & van Spronsen, F. J. (2021). Correlations of blood and brain biochemistry in phenylketonuria: Results from the Pah-enu2 PKU mouse. *Molecular Genetics and Metabolism*, *134*(3), 250–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymgme.2021.09.004>
- Fouche, J.-P., Groenewold, N. A., Sevenoaks, T., Heany, S., Lochner, C., Alonso, P., Batistuzzo, M. C., Cardoner, N., Ching, C. R. K., de Wit, S. J., Gutman, B., Hoexter, M. Q., Jahanshad, N., Kim, M., Kwon, J. S., Mataix-Cols, D., Menchon, J. M., Miguel, E. C., Nakamae, T., & Phillips, M. L. (2022). Shape analysis of subcortical structures in obsessive-compulsive disorder and the relationship with comorbid anxiety, depression, and medication use: A meta-analysis by the OCD Brain Imaging Consortium. *Brain and Behavior*, *12*(10), e2755. <https://doi.org/10.1002/brb3.2755>
- Gunduz, M., Arslan, N., Unal, O., Cakar, S., Kuyum, P., & Bulbul, S. (2015). Depression and anxiety among parents of phenylketonuria children. *Neurosciences*, *20*(4), 350–356. <https://doi.org/10.17712/nsj.2015.4.20150319>
- Leedy, P.D., & Ormrod, J.E. (2019). *Practical research: Planning and design* (12th ed.), Pearson
- Lou, H., Chen, J., & Liu, P. (2023). The impact of adolescents' health motivation on the relationship among mental stress, physical exercise, and stress symptoms during COVID-19: A dual moderation model. *Frontiers in Public Health*, *11*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1164184>
- Luo, L., Li, Q., You, W., Wang, Y., Tang, W., Li, B., Yang, Y., Sweeney, J. A., Li, F., & Gong, Q. (2021). Altered brain functional network dynamics in obsessive-compulsive disorder. *Human Brain Mapping*, *42*(7), 2061–2076. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.25345>

- Muri, R., Maissen-Abgottspon, S., Rummel, C., Rebsamen, M., Wiest, R., Hochuli, M., Jansma, B. M., Trepp, R., & Everts, R. (2022). Cortical thickness and its relationship to cognitive performance and metabolic control in adults with phenylketonuria. *Journal of Inherited Metabolic Disease*, *45*(6), 1082–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jimd.12561>
- Muri, R., Rummel, C., McKinley, R., Rebsamen, M., Maissen-Abgottspon, S., Kreis, R., Radojewski, P., Pospieszny, K., Hochuli, M., Wiest, R., Trepp, R., & Everts, R. (2024). Transient brain structure changes after high phenylalanine exposure in adults with phenylketonuria. *Brain*, *147*(11), 3863–3873. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awae139>
- Ntwatwa, Z., Lochner, C., Roos, A., Sevenoaks, T., Honk, J. van, Batistuzzo, M. C., Choi, S., Hoexter, M. Q., Kim, M., Kwon, J. S., Mataix-Cols, D., Menchón, J. M., Miguel, E. C., Takashi Nakamae, Carles Soriano-Mas, Veltman, D. J., Groenewold, N. A., van, Stein, D. J., & Ipser, J. (2025). Hippocampal and amygdala subfield volumes in obsessive–compulsive disorder by medication status. *Journal of Psychiatry and Neuroscience*, *50*(3), E170–E180. <https://doi.org/10.1503/jpn.230119>
- Ownby, R. L., Crocco, E., Acevedo, A., John, V., & Loewenstein, D. (2006). Depression and risk for Alzheimer’s disease. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, *63*(5), 530. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.63.5.530>
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., & McGuinness, L. A. (2021). PRISMA 2020 Explanation and elaboration: Updated Guidance and Exemplars for Reporting Systematic Reviews. *British Medical Journal*, *372*(160). NCBI. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>

- Pampaloni, I., Marriott, S., Pessina, E., Fisher, C., Govender, A., Mohamed, H., Chandler, A., Tyagi, H., Morris, L., & Pallanti, S. (2022). The global assessment of OCD. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, *118*(152342), 152342. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2022.152342>
- Pardo, J., Capdevila-Lacasa, C., Segura, B., Pané, A., Montserrat, C., Maria, Moreno, P. J., Glòria Garrabou, Grau-Junyent, J. M., Carme Junqué, Argudo-Ramírez, A., Barrau-Martínez, B., Cantó, J., Jaume Campistol, Francesc Cardellach, Climent Casals-Pascual, Chiva-Blanch, G., García-Arenas, D., Francesc Josep García-García, & Judit García-Villoria. (2024). Volumetric brain reductions in adult patients with phenylketonuria and their relationship with blood phenylalanine levels. *Journal of Neurodevelopmental Disorders*, *16*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s11689-024-09553-w>
- Parolisi, S., Montanari, C., Borghi, E., Cazzorla, C., Zuvadelli, J., Tosi, M., Barone, R., Bensi, G., Bonfanti, C., Vici, C. D., Biasucci, G., Burlina, A., Carbone, M. T., Verduci, E. (2023). Possible role of tryptophan metabolism along the microbiota-gut-brain axis on cognitive & behavioral aspects in Phenylketonuria. *Pharmacological Research*, *197*, 106952, ISSN 1043-6618, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2023.106952>.
- Thiele, A. G., Spieß, N., Ascherl, R., Arelin, M., Rohde, C., Kiess, W., & Beblo, S. (2021). Psychological well-being of early and continuously treated phenylketonuria patients. *JIMD Reports*, *59*(1), 69–80. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmd2.12202>
- Thomas, L., Aitkenhead, L., Stepien, K. M., Woodall, A., Macdonald, A., & Romani, C. (2024). Cognition and wellbeing in middle-aged early treated people with phenylketonuria: Preliminary results and methodological lessons. *Molecular Genetics*

and Metabolism Reports, 41, 101160–101160.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymgmr.2024.101160>

Wang, Z., Fontaine, M., Cyr, M., Rynn, M. A., Simpson, H. B., Marsh, R., & Pagliaccio, D. (2022). Subcortical shape in pediatric and adult obsessive-compulsive disorder.

Depression and Anxiety, 39(6), 504–514. <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.23261>

Woolf, L. I., & Adams, J. (2020). The early history of PKU. *International Journal of Neonatal Screening*, 6(3), 59. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijns6030059>

Wu, K., Wang, S., Ding, T., & Li, Y. (2023). The direct effect of exercise on the mental health of scientific and technological professionals and the mediating effects of stress, resilience, and social support. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1074418>

Xue, M., Shen, M., Wang, S., Pang, B., Zhang, X., Chen, K., Zhang, Z., & Niu, W.

(2025). Factors associated with psycho-behavioral problems among 100 children with phenylketonuria aged 6–18 years. *Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases*, 20(1).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-025-03824-y>

Zhang, L., Hu, X., Lu, L., Li, B., Hu, X., Bu, X., Li, H., Tang, S., Gao, Y., Yang, Y., Sweeney, J. A., Gong, Q., & Huang, X. (2020). Anatomic alterations across amygdala subnuclei in medication-free patients with obsessive–compulsive disorder. *Journal of Psychiatry and Neuroscience*, 45(5), 334–343. <https://doi.org/10.1503/jpn.190114>

Appendix A**Data Collection Table for the Frequency of Obsessive-Compulsive Behaviors**

Author & Year			
Sample size (n)			
PKU group size (n)			
Control group size (n)			
Measure method/scale			
Mean symptom score (PKU)			
Mean symptom score (control)			
SD of symptom score (PKU)			
SD of symptom score (control)			
Link to source			

Appendix B

Data Collection Table for Structural Changes in the Brain

Author & Year			
Sample size (n)			
Disorder studied			
Experimental group size (n)			
Control group size (n)			
Brain region analyzed			
Imaging tool			
Structural metric			
Units			
Mean value (experimental)			
Mean value (control)			
SD value (experimental)			
SD value (control)			
Link to source			

Appendix C

Pooled SD	$pooled\ SD = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)SD_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)SD_2^2}{n_1 + n_2 + 2}}$
Cohen's d	$d = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{pooled\ SD}$
Hedges' g	$g = d\left(1 - \frac{3}{4(n_1 + n_2) - 9}\right)$
Variance	$Var(g) = \frac{n_1 + n_2}{n_1 n_2} + \frac{g^2}{2(n_1 + n_2)}$
Weight	$w = \frac{1}{Var(g)}$
Pooled Hedges' g	$g_{pooled} = \frac{\Sigma(wg)}{\Sigma w}$

n_1 = the number of participants in the experimental group
 n_2 = the number of participants in the control group
 SD_1 = the standard deviation for the experimental group
 SD_2 = the standard deviation for the control group
 μ_1 = the mean value for the experimental group
 μ_2 = the mean value for the control group

Appendix D

Data Sheet (1 of 1): Behaviors

Thomas et al. (2024)	46	19	27	BAI	BAI = 12.2	BAI = 4.8	BAI = 10.4	BAI = 5.4	https://www.scie
Thomas et al. (2024)	46	19	27	BDI	10.4	4.4	8.4	4.4	https://www.scie
Albers et al. (2026)	99	29	79	PKU-QoL; "Sadness"	32.8	16.4	26	22.5	https://link.sprin
Gunduz et al. (2015)	97	61	36	BDI	12.3	5.4	9.1	4.1	https://pmc.ncbi

Data Sheet (1 of 2): Neurological Changes

Author & Year	Sample size (n)	Disorder studied	Experimental group size (n)	Control group size (n)	Brain region analyzed	Imaging tool	Structural metric	Units
Aldridge et al. (2020)	40	PKU	20	20	CGM, CWM	MRI	Volume	mm ³
Ntwatwa et al. (2025)	719	OCD	381	338	Hippocampus, amygdala	Structural MRI	Volume	mm ³
Zhang et al. (2020)	174	OCD	81	93	Left/right anterior amygdaloid area	Structural MRI	Volume	mm ³
Pardo et al. (2024)	57	PKU	35	22	Reductions in: hippocampus, amygdala, cortical gray matter, subcortical gray matter, cerebral white matter, mean cortical thickness	MRI	Volume	Unitless; ratio

Data Sheet (2 of 2): Neurological Changes

Mean value (experimental)	Mean value (control)	SD value (experimental)	SD value (control)	Link to source
CGM = 75820 CWM = 46398	CGM = 77285 CWM = 44395	CGM = 12977 CWM = 6799	CGM = 10664 CWM = 6031	http://sciencedir
Hippocampus = 3544.4 Amygdala = 1770.3	Hippocampus = 3587.5 Amygdala = 1783	Hippocampus = 340.4 Amygdala = 187.9	Hippocampus = 361.6 Amygdala = 198.1	https://pmc.ncbi
Left = 55 Right = 59	Left = 55 Right = 61	Left = 1 Right = 1	Left = 1 Right = 1	https://cdnscienc
0.273, 0.108, 32.097, 3.885, 14.676, 2.535	0.293, 0.116, 33.363, 4.069, 15.883, 2.521	0.023, 0.009, 2.166, 0.236, 1.129, 0.068	0.034, 0.012, 3.195, 0.379, 1.565, 0.080	https://link.sprin

Appendix E

Obsessive-Compulsive-Like Behavior	Validation Directly From the <i>DSM-5</i>
Repetitive Behaviors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Repetitive behaviors (e.g., hand washing, ordering checking) or mental acts (e.g., praying, counting, repeating words silently) that the person feels driven to perform in response to an obsession, or according to the rules that must be applied rigidly” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). - “...thought insertion or delusional preoccupations, as in schizophrenia spectrum and other psychotic disorders; or repetitive patterns of behavior” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).
Guilt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “...impulses, as in disruptive, impulse-control, and conduct disorders; guilty ruminations, as in major depressive disorder; thought insertion or delusional preoccupations” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).
Anxiety	<p>Overlapping or related symptom domains; not direct indicators of OCD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Recurrent and persistent thoughts, urges or images that are experienced, at some time during the disturbance, as intrusive, unwanted, and that in most individuals cause marked anxiety or distress” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).
Depression	<p>Overlapping or related symptom domains; not direct indicators of OCD.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “...guilty ruminations, as in major depressive disorder; thought insertion or delusional preoccupations, as in schizophrenia spectrum and other psychotic disorders” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). - “Recurrent and persistent thoughts, urges or images that are experienced, at some time during the disturbance, as intrusive, unwanted, and that in most individuals cause marked anxiety or distress” (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).